

Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI): Policy on Data Management

(MIRRI-ERIC Policies)

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Executive Summary

Microbial domain biological resource centres (mBRC) provide live cultures, their associate data and expertise to foster and support the development of basic and applied science. Based on a long tradition, individual not-for-profit mBRCs were established to add value to known and yet unknown microbial biodiversity and to exploit unknown sources and knowledge to discover and disclose for the bioeconomy and bioscience. For several decades, collaboration among some mBRCs resulted in the achievement of several common goals of mutual interest. The pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) has been established to go beyond these first hesitant collaborating attempts.

Directed by the MIRRI mission and user needs the current independent, often institutional policies and managed processes will be adapted by partner mBRCs to harmonize holdings, services, the training offer, accession policy and share expertise.

Better managed resources provided with legal compliance coupled with improved interaction with stakeholders will lead to further discovery in all areas of the Life Sciences. Therefore, a vision of knowledge transfer has been outlined to offer access to human expertise, to increase knowledge and promote professional development, and to provide a platform for long-term sustainability of microbial biodiversity. The knowledge transfer will be realized through a virtual Collaborative Working Environment inspiring excellence and to drive collaboration across borders and disciplines.

The following pages include the Policy on Data Management of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure MIRRI, a prerequisite for public mBRCs to join MIRRI as partners in the envisaged legal entity MIRRI-ERIC as indicated in the Partner Charter.

For more information on MIRRI please visit our website www.mirri.org.

MIRRI Policy on Data Management

To overcome the current situation, the MIRRI Information System (MIRRI-ERIC IS), as part of the Collaborative Working Environment (MIRRI-ERIC CWE), will be established deploying an integrated, high-quality, automatically validated, manually annotated, semantic-rich, non-redundant micro-biological resource database which provides all relevant information and associated contextual data (metadata) about a particular biological resource. MIRRI-IS will be designed as the central entry point for users, curators and developers that need access to the integrated knowledge of mBRCs and selected third party databases while assuring that the specific competences of partner mBRCs remain transparent. The aim is to establish a trademark for high quality data and expertise, which enhances the reputation of participating mBRCs. The MIRRI policy on data management is a commitment to a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) provision of data and information.

Requirements for mBRCs to comply with the MIRRI policy on data management:

To allow MIRRI-IS to be operational, MIRRI partners need to comply with:

1. Machine-readable mBRCs catalogues.
2. In case information is not digitally available yet, proper digitalization of key information needs to be undertaken.
3. Provision of accurate data.
4. The MIRRI Minimum Data Set (MIRRI MDS) of descriptors include 1) Strain Number, 2) Other Strain Number, 3) Present Name, 4) Organism Type, 5) Restrictions, 6) Status, 7) History of Deposit, 8) Growth conditions, 9) Form of supply, 10) Geographic Origin and 11) additional accession number(s) to link the data to the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), in case this is available. Besides these fundamental fields, specific “data packages” and additional subfields will be added over time to enrich the MDS. This will be extended towards a recommended data set (RDS) and finally full data set (FDS).
5. The content of the fields is expected to follow the guidelines, data model, controlled vocabularies and ontologies specified by the MIRRI consortium.
6. The final set of fields, including their expected content, will be consolidated in the Minimum Information about Biological Resources (MIaBRe) standard and checklist.
7. Curation level and quality of data needs to be assured by unified Standard Operating Procedures in mBRCs.
8. Provision of the data in a structured electronically available format.
9. For each biological resource, data need to be made available in machine-readable format and in regular time intervals. Over time, each mBRC in MIRRI should provide their data by Web Services in an XML based exchange language, e.g. based on the Microbiological Common Language (MCL) and its extensions.